

Covid-19 vaccines and potential spike protein mediated serious adverse events

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INTRODUCTION

SARS-CoV-2 is reported to cause a wide array of complications in various organ systems (Gupta et al. 2020), many of which are understood to be induced via the virus's spike protein which causes endothelial-cell injury via downregulation of ACE2 (Lei et al 2021). The toxicity of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein was not known during COVID-19 vaccine development or authorization process, with most approved COVID-19 vaccines triggering the generation of a version of this spike protein. This raises the question if the spike proteins generated by the COVID-19 vaccines are inducing endothelial cell injury leading to serious adverse events that produce complications similar to various manifestations of COVID-19. To investigate this question a post-hoc analysis was performed of the serious adverse events reported in the randomized controlled trials using a composite harm outcome which includes the various COVID-19 manifestations that are likely caused by the SARS-CoV2 spike protein.

METHODS/PROCEDURES

1. Choose source for composite endpoint

- Inclusive list of all COVID-19 manifestations independent of known mechanism (High Sensitivity) - [Gupta et al 2020](#)
- Brighton Collaboration ([Covid-19 AESI list](#)) endorsed by WHO ([PDF p.64](#))
- COVID-19 manifestations with identified ACE2 associated mechanisms - use [Gupta et al 2020](#)

2. Create composite endpoint by extracting from sources

- Two authors will independently create composite harm lists with any disagreement that can not be agreed on decided by a third clinician

3. Pull data from RCT SAE results tables

- Record source/URL
- Extract type, number of events per arm
- Record any reporting thresholds
- Create list of SAE descriptions blinded from results per group
- Data sources: FDA EUA memos, documents, Health Canada/EMA CSRs, **PD** could ask Moderna/Pfizer for SAE tables (with no reporting threshold)

4. Select included SAEs based on meeting composite endpoint

- Using the Blinded SAE list, two authors will independently choose SAEs to include in the composite harm outcome
- 2 clinicians independently, disagreements through consensus with 3rd clinician

5. Statistical Analysis

- Inter-rater reliability kappa value
- Estimate risk differences and 95% CIs
- Calculate between group differences
 - Within each individual clinical trial
 - Meta analysis across all spike protein vaccine trials
 - Meta analysis by vaccine delivery mechanism (mRNA vs Adenovirus)
 - Report I2 and p-value based on Cochrane Q-test for meta-analysis

Table 1. Composite endpoints

General manifestations of Covid-19: x, y, z,

ACE2 mediated manifestations: x, y, z,

Brighton: x, y, z,

Table 2. Serious adverse events

	Composite endpoints		
Trial (ages)	General manifestations of Covid-19	Brighton	ACE2 mediated manifestations
Pfizer (12-15y); NCT12345	a/b vs. x/y risk difference (CI)		
Pfizer (16+y)			
Moderna (12-17)			
Moderna (18+y); NCT04470427			
Janssen (18+y); NCT04505722			
AZ (18+y)			
Novavax (18+y)			
Sinopharm (18+)			
Meta-analysis	risk difference (CI) I2; p-value (Q test)		

mRNA vaccines			
Adenovirus vector vaccines			
Trials not included (reason)			